

EXAMINING THE EFFECT OF BANK-SPECIFIC FACTORS ON PUBLIC CONFIDENCE IN A MULTI-CURRENCY ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Globally, the banking sector continues to serve as a fundamental driver of economic growth and development primarily through its role in facilitating financial services to the manufacturing and industrial sectors. Nevertheless, there is continued liquidity challenges, financial stability concerns, infrastructure and technological constraints crippling efficient operation of the sector leading to low utilization of banking services by informal sector in Zimbabwe. Such a situation has constrained the financial intermediary role of banks of supplying affordable long-term loans to productive sectors of the economy as a catalyst for economic growth through the finance-growth nexus. Therefore, this study sought to provide an understanding of the effect of bank-specific factors on bank public confidence in Zimbabwe under the multiple currency system. The study adopted a quantitative research design and utilized secondary data which was analysed using EViews Software Package Version 7. Study findings revealed that non-performing loans (NPLs) has a significantly adverse effect on bank public confidence while liquidity, business intelligence and analytics, bank size, asset quality, and digitalization have a statistically significant and positive effect on bank public confidence. Thus, the study recommends banks to implement 'pay as you go' banking models to allow bank clients to only incur costs when a service is utilized as this will motivate and attract the informal sector into using formal banking system alleviating the liquidity position of the sector raising bank public confidence.

Keywords: Bank Public Confidence, Multiple Currency System, Bank Specific Factors, Hyperinflation, Liquidity, Zimbabwe.

1. INTRODUCTION

The banking industry remains a strong pillar that drives economic prosperity and development through provision of financial services to the manufacturing and industrial sector the world over (Levine, 2005). However, Zimbabwe's banking sector experienced a plethora of difficulties since the turn of the century and some of them include exchange rate volatility, crippling hyperinflation and a substantial decline in bank public confidence (Kabango and Franz, 2015). The economy gained short-lived stability when monetary authorities introduced a multiple currency system in 2009, but the banking industry has been plunged into yet another economic quagmire as it struggles to revive bank public confidence (Mukuddem-Petersen & Petersen, 2016).

Researchers agree that bank-specific factors, such as bank size, asset quality, and liquidity, significantly influence bank public confidence (Flannery, 1985; Hassan & Bashir, 2003). Many banks are increasingly adopting digital technologies and business intelligence, which have globally transformed the banking sector, offering both opportunities and challenges in rebuilding public trust (Davenport, 2006; Chavarnakul & Ketkar, 2017). Following recent banking crises, including the collapse of American Savings and Loan, Silicon Valley Bank, Signature Bank, and First Republic Bank, maintaining public confidence has become crucial to prevent bank runs. Public trust is vital for the proper functioning of individual banks, the banking industry, financial system stability, and the broader economy.

Despite the growing importance of public confidence in the banking industry, research on the topic remains scarce (Bijlsma et al., 2022). Specifically, there is limited research on the factors influencing public confidence in Zimbabwe's banking sector. Most prior studies have focused on macroeconomic factors like inflation and interest rates (Munjoma & Chipangura, 2016). Some studies have explored trust in bank personnel, financial health, the impact of Covid-19, or financial crises (Crujisen et al., 2021a). However, the role of bank-specific factors, such as digitalization and business intelligence, in shaping public confidence remains largely understudied.

This study therefore seeks to determine the effect of bank-specific factors, such as bank size, liquidity, business intelligence and analytics, asset quality and digitalization, on public confidence in Zimbabwe's banking sector. Gaining an appreciation of the association between each of these factors and bank public confidence is critical in informing strategies that authorities can implement to revive and maintain public confidence in the banking sector. This can basically support the development of a sound and efficient banking sector that contributes to Zimbabwe's economic prosperity and advancement, given the obtaining economic backward ness.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Perspective

This section explores theories explaining how bank-specific factors influence public confidence in banking. Key theories include the Trust Theory, Agency Theory, Signalling Theory, Stakeholder Theory, Institutional Theory, Diamond and Dybvig's 1983 banking model, and the Risk Perception Theory. However, this study focuses specifically on the Trust Theory.

2.1.1 The Trust Theory

Trust Theory, proposed by American psychologist Jack Gibb in 1978, is commonly known as the Trust Framework in financial contexts. It explains how trust is built and maintained in relationships, particularly between banks and their clients (Mollering, 2006). This conceptual framework details how trust is created and evaluated in various situations. Gibb (1978) asserts that trust is a fundamental human dynamic and a key factor in effective relationships. The theory is based on four core components: reliability, integrity,

emotional safety, and technical competence. Recent developments suggest that trust is formed through four key elements: trust, the trustor, risk, and the trustee. The trustee, in this case, is the bank, while the trustor is the client. Trust involves the willingness of the trustor to accept risk, with risk referring to uncertainty and potential negative consequences associated with trusting the trustee's actions.

Recent theorists have used the Trust Theory to examine how bank-specific factors impact public confidence (Davenport, 2006; Chavarnakul & Ketkar, 2017). Banks adopting digital technologies like AI, ecosystem banking, and robo services enhance public confidence by offering secure, convenient online services (Chavarnakul & Ketkar, 2017). Diamond and Dybvig (1983) argue that a bank's liquidity position influences public confidence, as clients trust banks that meet withdrawal demands. Hassan and Bashir (2003) further assert that a bank's size affects public confidence, with larger banks perceived as more secure and stable.

The adoption of business intelligence and analytics enhances public confidence, as clients trust banks that provide timely and accurate data (Davenport, 2006). A bank's asset quality also influences public confidence, with clients preferring banks with high-quality assets (Flannery, 1985). Banks must understand how these factors impact trust to develop strategies that build and maintain public confidence. The trust framework emphasizes the importance of trust between banks and clients, highlighting the role of bank-specific factors in fostering public confidence.

2.2 Conceptual Perspective

2.2.1 Conceptual Model

This study examined the relationship between bank-specific factors and public confidence in Zimbabwean banks. Bank public confidence is the dependent variable, while liquidity, business intelligence, asset quality, bank size, and digitalization are the predictor variables. The conceptual model used in this study is illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Source: Authors' Compilation

2.2.3 The concept of bank public confidence

Bank public confidence refers to the belief and trust that individuals have in the decisions made by authorities, such as the government (Donovan, 2012). Vickerstaff et al. (2012) define confidence as trust or assumptions that influence one's actions based on the expectations of another's behaviour. Rousseau et al. (1998) describe it as a psychological state where individuals accept exposure due to a positive view of another's intentions. Munoangira and Kaja (2016) define it as the unwavering conviction people have in their authorities' decisions, where customers trust that their money is safe in banks. This is reflected in deposit levels and the number of individuals using banking services. Similarly, Sapienza et al. (2013) explain public confidence as the expectation that others will act in a favourable way, despite the risk or inability to monitor their actions.

The Institute of Bankers in Zimbabwe (2011) defines bank public confidence as the belief and trust that stakeholders have in the safety of their money, which should be accessible when needed. Jureviciene and Skvarrciany (2014) describe confidence as the interaction between cognitive and behavioural aspects of human actions. This highlights that confidence and trust are closely related and used interchangeably in this study.

Earle (2009) defines public trust and confidence as expectations of positive outcomes from collective participation and mutual principles. Siegrist & Gutscher (2012) argue that confidence is nearly identical to trust in all areas of life. Shalimova (2014) highlights that trust in finance involves civility, reciprocity, predictability, collaboration based on integrity, and the absence of deceit. Guiso (2010) defines trust as the belief that the other party will honour their promise without exploiting the individual involved.

Fungacova et al. (2019) argue that trust in financial institutions is the expectation that banks are reliable and will honour their commitments. When a person deposits money, they expect it to be available when needed. A bank that fails to meet these expectations undermines public trust. This damages bank-customer relationships, potentially leading to bank runs and financial crises. Therefore, trust is crucial for fostering long-term, stable bank-customer relationships (Roberts-Lombard & Petzer, 2021).

Trust is a concept that varies across disciplines, often split into narrow-scope and broad-scope trust. Broad-scope trust refers to the general expectation that entities within a particular industry are reliable and will fulfil their commitments (Hansan, 2012). In contrast, narrow-scope trust focuses on the belief that a specific financial institution, such as a bank, is dependable and can be trusted to honour its promises. Both forms of trust are critical in shaping public confidence in the banking sector.

2.2.4 The concept of bank liquidity

Liquidity is crucial for any bank, as its shortage can disrupt banking operations (Ayinuola and Gumel, 2023). In banking literature, three main types of liquidity are identified: central bank liquidity, market liquidity, and funding liquidity (Yuan et al., 2022). A bank that fails to meet its short-term obligations is considered illiquid. When multiple banks within an industry experience prolonged illiquidity, it results in a liquidity crisis. This crisis is marked

by a severe lack of funding and market liquidity, leading to instability in the financial system (Borio and Drehmann, 2009). A liquidity crisis is often accompanied by a drop in asset prices, reduced market participation, and trading disruptions (Amihud et al., 2013; Brunnermeier, 2009). Thus, if a bank cannot meet its short-term liabilities, it faces liquidity risk (Ali & Puah, 2023).

2.2.5 The concept of business intelligence and analytics in banks

Business intelligence and analytics encompasses technologies, systems, and tools that help businesses understand data to improve operations, product development, customer relations, and competitive advantage (Al-Okaily et al., 2022; Ajah & Nweke 2019). According to Dresner (2003) as cited in Zitha and Ajigini (2023), it involves the scientific management of enterprise information. Business intelligence systems collect data from various sources and transform it into formats that support informed decision-making (Russman et al., 2017). It includes tools, applications, infrastructure, and best practices that enable data access and analysis for effective decision-making (Gartner, 2019).

Azvine et al. (2005) categorized business intelligence tools into three groups: predictive modelling, customer behaviour analysis, and reporting/visualization tools (trend analysis). They emphasized that meaningful business intelligence relies on three main technologies: data warehouses, analytical tools, and reporting tools. Business intelligence and analytics enable banks to leverage data for informed decision-making, operational optimization, and personalized customer experiences. The primary goal in banking is to enhance decision-making speed and accuracy (Zitha & Ajigini, 2023). The internet, along with emerging technologies like AI and data mining, has further bolstered bank public confidence (D. Yu, 2021).

2.2.6 The concept of bank asset quality

Bank asset quality refers to the performance and stability of a bank's assets, including investments and mortgage bundles, and its ability to generate anticipated revenue from these resources. Key factors include credit class, off-balance sheet commitments, and investment quality (World Bank, 2022). It is influenced by default, operational, systemic, compliance, and liquidity risks. Asset quality is measured by ratios such as non-performing loans to total loans, provisioning coverage, return on assets, loan loss provisioning, and net interest margin (Dzingirai & Katuka, 2014). Non-performing loans are those overdue by 90 days. Berhanu (2015) states that an increase in non-performing loans hinders banking sector development by reducing depositor confidence and liquidity.

El-Chaarani (2022) asserts that the quality of a bank's loans determines its liquidity, while Gorter and Bloem (2001) suggest that poor asset quality diminishes depositor confidence. Continued deterioration in asset quality can lead to bank runs due to eroded public trust. Poor asset quality also reduces efficiency, profit margins, and heightens risk, attracting more regulatory scrutiny and depleting a bank's capital base (Melese, 2015). Banks with solid asset quality perform better, fostering industry development (Al-Homaidi et al., 2018). Dzingirai and Katuka (2014) argue that banks with high non-performing loans risk underdevelopment and eventual failure. Non-performing loans primarily result from poor

borrower screening and weak governance (European Central Bank, 2017). The issue of non-performing loans remains unresolved since the early 2000s (Naili & Lahrichi, 2022).

2.2.7 The concept of bank size

Bank size entails the vastness of or intensity of a banking firm's activities, normally computed using several indicators. Capitalization levels, bank deposits, total bank assets, levels of bank loans, total bank earnings, branch networks and bank staff levels are some of the indicators. However, most literature, identified total assets as the most common measures of bank size that affects the development of banks by determining bank profitability (Adelopo et al., 2018; Zolkifili et al., 2019; Ali & Puaah, 2019; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2016). Systematically Important Financial Institutions (SIFI), community banks, national banks, regional banks and global banks are the most common types of bank sizes in literature (World Bank, 2022).

Bank size can also be categorized into small and large banks. Effects of bank size include risk management, economies of scale, innovation, regulation and competition. Bank size substantially affects operations, stability and fortitude of banking firms. Large banks can enjoy economies of scale hence ability to enjoy low total average costs leading to their development (Bolarinwa et al., 2019 & Sahyouni et al., 2018). Information gathering and processing costs are some of the economies of scale that large banks enjoy. An appreciation of bank size is imperative in scrutinizing bank risk, performance and strategic decisions.

2.2.8 The concept of digital banking

Digital banking refers to the shift from analog to digital data sets (Stepantseva, 2022; Rachinger et al., 2018). It involves the transformation of a bank's model through the adoption of digital tools and applications to enhance performance (Legner et al., 2017; Ilicus, 2018). According to Digital Business Consultancy, i-SCOOP (2016), digital banking is the use of digital technology and data to improve business, generate revenue, and redesign business processes for a more digital-oriented environment. Schallmo and Williams (2018) describe it as fundamental changes to business models based on insights gained from advanced digitization efforts.

Digital banking is enabled by the integration of technologies such as cloud computing, big data, blockchain, robo services, and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). It involves providing banking services that allow clients to conduct transactions through internet and online technologies, enhancing client value and satisfaction (Indriasari et al., 2022). Innovations in digital banking are driven by technologies like artificial intelligence, cloud banking, and the Internet of Things, which automate processes and offer smarter banking services. APIs facilitate cross-institutional transactions, fostering a digital ecosystem across integrated bank channels. With technology deeply embedded in modern culture, manual processes have become outdated. According to Kitsios et al. (2021), digital transformation continuously impacts both the internal and external business environments, compelling banks to redesign their operations and processes.

2.3 Empirical Perspective

Prior related studies on the subject matter of bank public confidence were reviewed in this section with a view of developing research hypotheses.

2.3.1 The effect of liquidity on bank public confidence

A strand of literature examines the effect of liquidity on bank public confidence. Kalanidis (2016) confirmed that liquidity issues arising from crises can trigger bank runs and erode public confidence, as banks may struggle to provide funds on time, increasing liquidity risk. Additionally, the Financial Stability Board (2022) highlighted that liquidity influences bank public confidence by preventing rapid outflows of customer funds during financial instability.

A study by Ratri (2021) confirmed that poor liquidity management leads to liquidity risk, which negatively affects bank public confidence. Similarly, Nyamador (2021) emphasized that efficient liquidity is crucial for the survival and growth of banks by fostering public confidence. However, Makandwa (2016) found that liquidity crises negatively impact bank public confidence in Zimbabwe. In contrast, van der Crujisen et al. (2020) argued that liquidity does not significantly influence bank public confidence. The study further noted that individuals' perceptions of a bank's liquidity situation directly affect their confidence in the bank. Following this discussion, it is therefore hypothesized that:

H₁: Liquidity has a positive effect on bank public confidence.

2.3.2 The effect of business intelligence and analytics on bank public confidence.

There is a strand of literature that explains how business intelligence and analytics influence bank public confidence. A study by Aldboush and Ferdous (2023) confirmed that business intelligence and data analytics adversely influence bank public confidence. This study further highlighted that use of big data analytics raises ethical and privacy concerns among bank clients in the banking industry. Thus, the study found out that data breaches impair bank trust and there is need for transparency in data collection, processing and analysis with a view to maintain client confidence and credibility before using the data for banks' decision making.

A study by KPMG (2016) confirmed that data analytics can enhance consumer trust and confidence in banks. Similarly, Hmoud et al. (2023) highlighted the role of business intelligence in fostering bank public confidence, noting that high-quality information is crucial. Basaran and Bagheri (2020) further emphasized that interruptions in data generation worsen financial instability, leading to diminished confidence. Their research found that poor information handling and analytics can trigger bank runs and panic, further eroding public trust. Following this discussion, it is therefore hypothesized that:

H₂: Business intelligence and analytics influences banking sector development

2.3.3 The effect of asset quality on bank public confidence

A body of literature discusses the impact of asset quality on bank public confidence. Hoshimov (2022) found that non-performing loans negatively affect public trust in banks.

Similarly, Chernykh and Davydov (2019) confirmed that an increase in non-performing assets diminishes bank public confidence. Ampudia and Palligkinis (2018) noted that banks with fewer loan defaults are seen as financially stronger, boosting shareholder value. In contrast, Katuka (2023) emphasized that excessive loan defaults undermine public confidence and can lead to bank runs.

Balgova et al. (2017) confirmed that loan defaults damage bank public confidence by tying up capital, reducing credit supply, and distorting credit allocation. John (2018) supported this, stating that credit defaults indirectly erode trust by triggering the failure of multiple banks. Nsobilla (2016) echoed this view, noting that credit defaults harm public confidence among stakeholders. Chand et al. (2023) provided evidence that a rise in credit defaults and written-off loans increases banks' vulnerability to losing public trust. Nyasaka (2023) also emphasized that credit defaults reduce trust from depositors and foreign investors. Following this discussion, this study hypothesizes that:

H₃: Asset quality has a negative effect on bank public confidence.

2.3.4 The effect of bank size on bank public confidence.

Extant literature exists that explains how bank size affects bank public confidence. A study by Chernykh et al. (2019) on the issue of monetary steadiness and bank public confidence confirmed that bank size has a significantly adverse effect on bank public confidence. Moreso, another study by Berger et al. (2019) confirmed that large financial entities capable of proffering a wide assortment of products and facilities have a significant comparative advantage in generating bank public trust than smaller banks. This study further coined that large banks have economies of scale which allows them to offer more attractive deposit and loan rates to consumers culminating in high bank public trust.

Bijlsma et al. (2022) found that bank public confidence is lower among clients of smaller banks compared to larger ones. However, Hurley et al. (2014) found that smaller banks, such as zonal and cooperative banks in the U.S., have higher public confidence than larger ones. In Zimbabwe, Mwatetsera et al. (2022) confirmed that bank size positively influences public confidence. Similarly, Fungáčová & Weill (2017) affirmed the positive impact of bank size on public trust. Based on these findings, it is hypothesized that:

H₄: Bank size has a positive effect on bank public confidence.

2.3.5 The effect of digitalization on bank public confidence.

A strand of literature explores how digitalization impacts bank public confidence. Melnyk (2023) confirmed that digitalization drives confidence among younger patrons (18-35 years), with social networks and social approval positively influencing trust. However, the World Economic Forum (2018) cautioned that digitalization can cause unease among clients, leading to a decline in bank trust and limiting the benefits for banking institutions.

Bijlsma et al. (2022) confirmed that digitalization positively impacts bank public trust, with digitally literate customers showing higher confidence. Manhando & Towo (2023) also found that digitalization significantly enhances bank public confidence. Similarly, Shah

(2022) affirmed that digitalization has a positive effect on bank public trust. Based on these findings, it is therefore hypothesized that:

H₅: Digitalization has a positive effect on bank public confidence.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Data Sources and Description of Variables

This study utilized a quantitative research design. The study opted for this research design to establish the causal relationships between study variables, and it was also preferred on the basis that it integrates theory with empirical observations and allows analysis of numerical data. This study utilized secondary data for the period 2009 – 2023. Secondary data was preferred because it allows replicability of study by other authors. Data was mainly gathered from the World Bank online database with the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe (RBZ), International Monetary Fund (IMF), Zimbabwe Statistical Agency (ZIMSTATS) and Ministry of Finance and Economic Development as supplementary data sources.

The study treated bank public confidence (PBC) as the dependent variable and this variable was measured using increases in bank deposits. Liquidity, bank size, business intelligence and analytics, asset quality and digitalization were treated as independent variables as shown in table 1 below. In coming up with these most relevant independent variables, researcher relied on literature and the situation obtaining in the Zimbabwean economy. The data was then analysed using EViews version 7 software package.

Table 1: Justification of Study Variables

Identifier	Variable Description	Proxy	Supporting Literature	Anticipated sign
PBC	Bank Public Confidence	Percentage increase in deposits	Kibirango, (1999); Munoangira and Kaja (2016); USAID (2001).	Dependent Variable
LQ	Liquidity	Loan-to-total assets ratio	Dzingirai and Katuka (2014); Al-Matari (2023); Zolkifli et al., 2019.	(+)
BS	Bank Size	Natural logarithm of total assets	Dzingirai and Katuka (2014); Al-Matari (2023); Ali and Puah (2023); Bushashe (2023).	(+)
AQ	Asset Quality	Percentage increase in total loans divided by non-performing loans	Dzingirai and Katuka (2014); Al-Matari (2023); Abel and Le Roux (2017).	(-)
BIA	Business Intelligence and Analytics	Return on Investment	Negash and Gray (2008).	(+)
DIG	Digitalization	Number of individuals using internet banking	Sha'ban et al., (2020); Evans (2018); Kouladoum et al., (2022).	(+)

Source: Authors' Compilation

3.2 Model Specification

The researcher utilized an Ordinary Least Squares Method (OLS). Before running the regressions using ordinary least squares method, certain diagnostic tests were performed to test the set of assumptions and ensure robust regression results are obtained. This also aided in avoiding spurious regression results. Thus, unit root test, heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, autocorrelation, normality test and stability diagnostics were performed. The following multiple regression equation was estimated:

$$PBC_t = \alpha + \beta_1 \ln BS_{t-1} + \beta_2 AQ_{t-1} + \beta_3 BIA_{t-1} + \beta_4 DIG_{t-1} + \beta_5 LO_{t-1} + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (2.1)$$

Where $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_5$ are regression coefficients to be estimated, α is the constant and ε is the error term.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	BPC	LQ	BS	AQ	BIA	DIG
Mean	4.5124	2.12990	3.1519	3.3709	4.7077	4.4496
Median	10.2121	35.4423	5.4270	9.5018	4.9725	19.1237
Maximum	14.6500	34.5618	5.2740	6.3421	55.1272	50.3267
Minimum	35.7001	19.4398	2.4238	1.3728	42.5673	34.7561
Std. Dev.	0.9624	0.8501	0.9508	0.9242	0.7826	0.9096
Skewness	0.0168	0.2318	0.1034	1.1001	2.0741	0.8761
Kurtosis	1.2529	1.4564	2.3901	3.4250	5.1267	2.4158
Jarque-Bera	3.2400	2.6464	2.8001	2.2701	7.7039	3.1091
Probability	0.2912	0.3434	0.6403	0.6801	0.4301	0.6710
Sum	255.1004	325.0079	3.5221	7.2450	53.9170	712.1091
Sum Sq. Dev.	343540.0001	495.2483	6.5649	2.1312	331899.4002	2412.6704
Observations	15	15	15	15	15	15

Source: EViews Software Package (Version 7)

Table 2 shows the generally used statistics in this study. Business Intelligence and Analytics has the lowest standard deviation of 0.7826 and this indicates that it has a high degree of reliability pertaining its contribution in explaining public confidence variations in the Zimbabwean banking sector.

The mean (BPC) is 4.51 (45%) which shows that public confidence in Zimbabwe's banking sector is relatively low when compared with those of other nations on a scale of 1-10 since it is way too far below the recommended minimum threshold of 50 percent. The mean liquidity is very low at 21.3 percent, an indication that most banks are facing liquidity problems in the sector.

As shown in table 2 above, all the variables used in this study are normally distributed at a five percent level of significance as supported by their Jarque-Bera probability which is greater than 0.05.

4.2 Diagnostic Tests

4.2.1 Unit Root Test

Table 3: Unit Root Test Results

Variable(s)	ADF test	Mackinnon value	Prob	Order of integration	Decision
PBC	-7.4056	-3.4567	0.0000	1(2)	Stationary @ 1 %
LQ	-6.4657	-3.2345	0.0000	1(1)	Stationary @ 1 %
BS	-5.2345	-3.1239	0.0030	1(1)	Stationary @ 1 %
AQ	-5.3456	-3.6751	0.0020	1(1)	Stationary @ 1 %
BIA	-6.9871	-3.4326	0.0040	1(1)	Stationary @ 1 %
DIG	-5.1027	-3.2349	0.0058	1(1)	Stationary @ 1 %

Source: EViews Software Package (Version 7)

The unit root test results in Table 3 indicate that all variables achieved stationarity at the 1% significance level, as their ADF test statistics are more negative than the MacKinnon critical values. PBC (Public Bank Confidence) is stationary at the second difference (I (2)), requiring double differencing to achieve stationarity. LQ (Liquidity), BS (Bank Size), AQ (Asset Quality), BIA (Business Intelligence and Analytics), and DIG (Digitalization) are stationary at the first difference (I(1)). The significant p-values (< 0.01) confirm the rejection of the null hypothesis of non-stationarity, validating the data for time-series modelling. This ensures reliable and accurate empirical analysis of the variable relationships.

4.2.2 Other Study Diagnostic Tests

Table 4: Diagnostic Test Results for Heteroscedasticity, Autocorrelation, Stability, and Multicollinearity

1. Heteroscedasticity Test Results: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test		F-statistic = 0.7015	Prob. F (5,15) = 0.6832
2. Autocorrelation Test Results: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test and (Durbin Watson Test = 2.01)		F-statistic = 0.7074	Prob. F (2,14) = 0.6585
3. Stability Test Results: Chow Break Point Test		F-statistic = 0.5072	Prob. F (6,10) = 0.8582
4. Multicollinearity Test Results: Variance Inflation Factors			
Variable (s)	Coefficient Variance	Uncentered VIF	Centred VIF
LQ	5.3923	5.0325	2.7567
BS	3.0915	4.6130	6.6543
AQ	4.7017	6.3183	4.7864
BIA	3.1149	2.8937	1.8906
DIG	5.2036	5.6324	4.0980

Source: EViews Software Package (Version 7)

Table 4 shows diagnostic test results for autocorrelation, multicollinearity, stability and heteroscedasticity tests. The results of Breusch-Pagan Godfrey Test show that the problem of heteroscedasticity did not exist at a five percent level of significance because

F-statistic probability (0.6832) is far greater 0.05. VIF coefficients for multicollinearity test are all below 10, suggesting that all the variables used in the study were free from the problem of multicollinearity. The results of Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test show that the problem of autocorrelation did not exist at a five percent level of significance because F-statistic probability (0.6585) is far greater 0.05. Results of Chow break point test show that data was stable over time and there were no breaks at a five percent level of significance because F-statistic probability (0.8582) is far greater 0.05.

4.2.3 Regression Analysis

Table 5: Regression Results

Variable(s)	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	Prob
C	12.4562	29.4142	-0.3749	0.8712
LQ	7.9245	11.4001	6.7442	0.0000*
BS	5.4801	7.7808	3.4057	0.0022*
AQ	-3.1647	8.8909	-0.5018	0.0014*
BIA	2.1058	5.8479	-1.8829	0.0001*
DIG	6.2369	6.5875	-3.9483	0.0018*
R ²	0.8123			
Adjusted R ²	0.8061			
F-statistic	35.1442			
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000			
Schwarz Criterion	12.3286			
*Significant @ 1%, **Significant @ 5%, *** Significant at 5%				

Source: EViews Software Package (Version 7)

Using the statistics obtained in the regression model in Table 5, the new model becomes as follows:

Bank Public Confidence = 12.4562 + 7.9245 LQ + 5.4801 BS – 3.1647 AQ + 2.1058 BIA + 6.2369 DIG.

4.2.4 Interpretation of R-Squared and Adjusted R-Squared

The study obtained an R-Squared of 0.8123 and this means that approximately 81.23% of the explanatory variables adopted in the model managed to explain changes happening in the response variable. This makes the model a good one and an adjusted R-Squared coefficient of 0.8061 shows that approximately 80.61% of the response variable managed to explain changes happening in the explanatory variables. Study also obtained an F-statistic of 35.1442 which is by far greater than the 5 recommended by literature hence this model was good fit for estimation.

4.2.5 Discussion of Regression Results

The main objective of the study was to ascertain the effect of bank-specific factors on bank public confidence and all the directional hypotheses tested in this study were then extracted from this objective. Results obtained in this study ($\beta = 7.9245$; p value = 0.000)

are in support of the idea that liquidity has a statistically significant and positive effect on bank public confidence. These results insinuate that, as the liquidity condition of banks improves, bank public confidence also increases by a similar corresponding magnitude. Such results are consistent with those of prior related studies (Nyamador, 2021; IMF, 2010; Ngwu, 2006).

Possible reasons could be the fact that currently, liquidity that used to be a severe problem in Zimbabwe is now under control and the situation has slightly improved. Banks can now meet the liquidity limits of their clients with ease unlike around the years 2015 to 2018 when Zimbabwe's banking sector was having severe liquidity challenges emanating from the use of bond notes and coins as supported in some prior related studies that found a negative effect (Kalanidis, 2016; Ratri, 2021; Makandwa, 2016).

Study findings ($\beta = 5.4801$; $p = 0.0022$) support that business intelligence and analytics significantly and positively influence bank public confidence. As banks enhance their use of business intelligence, public confidence improves. This aligns with previous studies (KPMG, 2016; Hmoud et al., 2023). The well-established data policy in Zimbabwe ensures data privacy, fostering confidence by preventing breaches. Additionally, business intelligence helps detect fraud, offer personalized products, and ensure service reliability, further boosting sector confidence.

Study findings ($\beta = -3.1647$; $p = 0.0014$) support that asset quality negatively affects bank public confidence. As non-performing loans increase, stakeholder confidence declines. These results align with theoretical and empirical studies (Hoshimov, 2022; Davydov, 2019; Katuka, 2023; Balgova et al., 2017; John, 2018; Nsobilla, 2016; Chand et al., 2023; Murtin et al., 2018). In Zimbabwe's banking sector, non-performing loans have been decreasing at an accelerating rate, despite remaining below the five percent threshold.

Empirical evidence ($\beta = 5.4801$; $p = 0.0022$) supports the assertion that bank size positively impacts bank public confidence. These findings align with prior studies (Berger et al., 2019; Mwatetsera et al., 2022; Fungacova & Weill, 2017; Bülbül, 2013; Jureviciene & Skvarrciany, 2013). The Zimbabwean banking system, dominated by a few large banks, benefits from economies of scale, enabling them to effectively address customer complaints and offer a wide range of products and services. Large banks are better equipped to manage customer interactions, fostering greater sector confidence.

Research findings ($\beta = 6.2369$; $p = 0.0018$) provide empirical evidence that digitalization has a significant and positive influence on bank public confidence. These results suggest that as banks embrace digital banking, customer experience and convenience improve, thereby boosting confidence in the sector. The findings align with prior studies (Melnyk, 2023; Bijlsma et al., 2022; Manhando & Towo, 2023; Shah, 2022; Ahmed et al., 2020; Mwatetsera et al., 2022).

A potential reason could be that most bank clients in Zimbabwe's urban areas are highly educated and prefer customized digital services, enhancing their client experience. In contrast, rural populations, less reliant on banks, face challenges in digital banking, which may limit digitalization's broader impact.

5. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of the study was to identify bank-specific factors influencing bank public confidence in Zimbabwe under the multi-currency environment. The results revealed that liquidity, business intelligence and analytics, bank size, asset quality, and digitalization are key factors influencing bank public confidence. The study showed that liquidity, business intelligence and analytics, digitalization, and bank size have a statistically significant positive effect on bank public confidence.

Conversely, asset quality was found to have a significant negative effect on bank public confidence. The introduction of the multi-currency system initially stabilized prices, improving bank public confidence and enabling banks to refine their internal environments and strengthen their financial intermediation roles. However, with the introduction of local currencies like the bond note and coins in 2016 and the ZIG in 2023, monetary discipline weakened, leading to economic volatility and diminished investor confidence. As a result, many correspondent banks withdrew from the country, reducing foreign inflows into the banking sector.

The study, therefore, recommends that the Zimbabwean government needs to consider the sentiments of its citizens when formulating policies to regain the trust of its citizens. There is also a need for policy consistency to gain the confidence of its stakeholders. Apart from that, there is also a need for capacity building to boost productivity, augmenting bank liquidity.

The study also recommends that banks should implement 'pay as you go' banking models to allow bank clients to only incur costs when a service is utilized as this will motivate and attract the informal sector into using the formal banking system alleviating the liquidity position of the sector raising bank public confidence.

Authors' contributions

All authors made active participation in the development of the paper until approval of the final article for publication.

Lasten Mudzingwa¹: Study conception, data collection, and writing for the original draft.
Kudzana Matowanyika²: Crafting the methodology, formal analysis, and data validation.
Rangarirai Mbizi³: Data curation, visualisation, and software management.
David Chikwere⁴: Review, editing of the final version of the manuscript and supervision.

Data availability statement

The data that support study findings are available from the corresponding author on request.

Ethical Statement

The data are publicly available and there are no ethical restrictions.

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